

Towards the federation of digital collections within the arts and humanities

Concept of a generic integration model for
semi-structured research data

Projektarbeit

Im Virtuellen Weiterbildungsstudiengang Wirtschaftsinformatik

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Acronyms

AHDS	Arts and Humanities Data Service
CDWA	Categories for the Description of Works of Art
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CSV	Comma-separated values
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DC	Dublin Core Metadata Element Set
DCES	Dublin Core Metadata Element Set
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DTD	Document Type Definition
EpiDoc	Epigraphic Documents in TEI XML
EU	European Union
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MARC	Machine Readable Cataloguing
MDA	Model-driven architecture
MEI	Music Encoding Initiative

MODS	Metadata Object Description Schema
MOF	Meta Object Facility
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OCLC	Online Computer Library Center
SGML	Standard Generalized Markup Language
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UTF-8	8-Bit Universal Character Set Transformation Format
VRA	Visual Resources Association
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WWW	World Wide Web
XLink	XML Linking Language
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XPath	XML Path Language
XSLT	XSL Transformation (XSLT)
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

1

Chapter

Introduction

With the beginning evolution of the *digital humanities*, the field of *humanities computing* has been extended from computer science being applied on linguistic research to an interdisciplinary field that comprehensively focuses on the advancement of digital methods for their use within the diverse spectrum of the arts and humanities (HOCKEY 2004, 13-17). Methods, applications and standards have been created in order to facilitate the digitization, analysis and description of objects, resulting in digital representations such as scanned books and photographs of paintings. In addition, research data has been accumulated in numerous academic projects, which enriches objects in their physical or digital forms.

Research objects of the arts and humanities are traditionally stored in museums, archives and libraries, which often restrict physical access in order to preserve cultural heritage. Based on technical capabilities, digital collections generate the immediate benefits of location-independence and—by following the open access paradigm—public accessibility of research data. The increasing amount of openly published data thus results in a need for integrative services, which facilitate the discovery of collections and contained data. Examples such as OAIster¹ and Europeana² provide users with integrated views on heterogeneous data by providing a search over distributed collections. Following a traditional concept of data integration, which can be defined as "the problem of combining data residing

¹ <http://oaister.worldcat.org>

² <http://www.europeana.eu>

at different sources, and providing the user with a unified view of these data" (LENZERINI 2002, 233) the services are based on the selection of an integrative model to which the heterogeneous local schemata are connected. Despite conceptual and technological differences, the central idea of such services consists in the association of source data to an integrative model that is either (1) generic and easily reusable by abstracting from the specifics of original data or (2) has been defined with respect to a particular target community.

Opposed to existing approaches, this thesis considers the whole spectrum of the arts and humanities as an application domain for data integration. The inherent heterogeneity of disciplines, research questions and digital collections results in numerous integrative use-cases—with information needs ranging from a focus on a limited set of collections to broad and interdisciplinary scenarios. As a result, the a-priori analysis of the composition and relevance of collections and concepts is not possible, which thus prevents the definition of a specific unifying view in the sense of traditional integration architectures that conform to the theoretical perspective of LENZERINI (2002).

For this reason, the primary goal of this thesis contains in the definition of a theoretic model for the representation of schemata and their semantic correlations in order to facilitate data federation for implementing services. Abstracting from the technological specifics of data integration and emphasizing the particular focus on semantic aspects, the thesis is based on the central assumption that the explication of the knowledge of domain experts is required to continuously evolve an integrative system to satisfy the use-cases in an evolutionary fashion.

The term federation is deliberately chosen to reflect a virtual and possibly temporary form of data integration: in the interpretation of this thesis, data in the federated system needs to remain citeable and hence unmodified to respect the character and intent of research data. The usage of the term integration throughout this thesis relates to this restricted form.

Structure of the thesis

After this introduction, chapter 2 introduces the background of the research data landscape of the arts and humanities, which can be characterized by the publication

of semi-structured data. The problem area of data integration is classified into technological and context-specific aspects with respect to the expert groups of computer scientists and scholars and their respective explicable knowledge.

Details on the relevant context of the arts and humanities are presented in chapter 3, including an analysis of typical digital collections and schemata that are applied to containing data. Current approaches to data integration are compared with respect to the addressed granularity and the amount of considered disciplines, after which central conclusions of the context and abstract use-cases of a generic integration model are presented.

The developed theoretical concept in chapter 4 elaborates—after initial ideas on a conceptual architecture are presented—the generic and semantically enriched representation of schemata, which are then related by mappings in order to establish semantic interoperability. The concept concludes with an inheritance strategy that addresses scalability considerations.

The summary in chapter 5 finally summarizes the key findings of this thesis.

2

Chapter

Background

This chapter provides an introduction to aspects, which are considered fundamental for the conceptual work of this thesis: Due to the focus on digital collections and their provided types of resources, the concept of *semi-structured data* will be introduced on an abstract level, followed by the description of important formats. Based on the heterogeneity levels according to [LESER & NAUMANN \(2007, 60-78\)](#), the background of *data integration* is then classified and explained in terms of technological and context interoperability.

2.1 Semi-structured data

The formal layout and constraints of *structured data* are explicitly specified in terms of data models, which are required for the interpretation of the data they define. A common application of structured data can be found in relational databases, where data is maintained in separation from its formal specification ([ABITEBOUL 2009, 2599](#)). In contrast, *unstructured data* such as natural texts are characterized by the absence of such pre-defined constraints. *Semi-structured data* can be represented by graph- or tree-like structures ([BUNEMAN 1997, 118](#)), conforms to an inherent layout, but does not depend on the existence of an external schema: "In semistructured data, the information that is normally associated with a schema is contained within the data, which is sometimes called *self-describing*." ([BUNEMAN 1997, 117](#))

Reusable semi-structured data models are often specified, if a set of documents³ share a common structure against which the validation of such documents should be performed. Aside from document validation, the definition of external data models provides a benefit with respect to the semantic interpretation of data and is particularly important for data integration: with a knowledge about the model, i.e. the concepts it addresses, the interpretation of the set of conforming instances is facilitated—both for humans and computing systems.

With the emergence of the *World Wide Web (WWW)* and *Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)*, means to publish and browse unstructured content in the form of websites became publicly available. The language of *HTML* is predefined with regard to the goal of describing the structure and layout of web pages. As a result of the limitations of *HTML* for the definition of structured content, formats dedicated to data publication and exchange have been developed, among which the *Extensible Markup Language (XML)*—being like *HTML* a subset of the *Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML)*—gained wide acceptance. As a result of the historical development, the terms of semi-structured data and *XML* are often used interchangeably (ABITEBOUL 2009, 2599).

2.1.1 XML

Whereas semi-structured data constitutes an abstract concept for representing data in the forms of graphs or trees (BUNEMAN 1997, 118), *XML* (BRAY ET AL. 2006) is a markup language for the representation of semi-structured constraints and content in terms of *XML* documents. The structure and layout of *XML* is therefore encoded in *markup* (such as start-tags, end-tags and empty-element tags), whereas the remainder of documents (including comments, processing instructions, parsed and unparsed data) is considered as *character data* (BRAY ET AL. 2006, Sect. 2.4). Based on *XML*, the *World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)* has installed various working groups and developed a family of languages that facilitate various aspects of the interaction with *XML* documents. Examples of such specifications⁴ can be

³ Semi-structured data is organized in terms of documents, which can be considered as conceptual equivalents to tuples in relational databases

⁴ Please see the web-pages of the respective working groups <http://www.w3.org/XML/> for further reference

found in some prominent W3C recommendations:

- *XML Schema*⁵ is specified by two W3C recommendations and describes a schema language for the expression of constraints and rules to which an XML document needs to conform in order to be considered as valid.
- *Namespaces in XML* enables a qualification of element and attribute names with the help of namespaces.
- *XSL Transformation (XSLT)* (XSLT) defines a language for the transformation of XML documents into other XML documents.
- *XML Path Language (XPath)* is a language that allows to address parts of XML documents.
- *XML Linking Language (XLink)* facilitates the creation of links between XML documents.

Among numerous other standards, these W3C recommendations extend the functionality and expressiveness of XML, but also increase the complexity of the XML language realm.

2.1.2 JSON, YAML

Despite the undiminished significance of XML for data exchange, other standards for the description of semi-structured data such as *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)* or *YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML)* have evolved as alternatives—especially for cases where the complexity of a markup language is not required. Figure 2.1 shows semantically equivalent representations of an exemplary, simple resource described in terms of XML, JSON and YAML. Please note that this example is not intended to compare the applicability of standards for the description of semi-structured data in general, but simply indicates the existence of multiple such standards of which data providers can select to publish their data. The figure also reflects the self-describing nature of semi-structured data as the examples each include information on the structure of the embodied content and are thus considered human-readable.

JSON⁶ is a simple data exchange format based on the JavaScript Program-

⁵ To prevent terminological confusion, the specification will be addressed as W3C XML Schema in contrast to the derived XML schemata

⁶ <http://www.json.org>

Figure 2.1: Example record in equivalent XML, JSON and YAML representations

ming Language and is—despite its origins—considered as generic and language-independent. The structural aspects of JSON can be found in figure 2.1b: Objects are denoted with curly braces (`{ ... }`), in which the properties of the object are described by comma separated lists of name/value pairs. Arrays are enclosed by square brackets (`[...]`) and contain a comma separated list of values. Whereas names are in JSON always encoded as strings, available data types consist of strings, numbers, objects, arrays, the boolean expressions `true` and `false`, and `null`. A proposal for a JSON schema specification (GALIEGUE ET AL. 2013) has been submitted to the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF).

Another popular format for the specification of semi-structured data consists in YAML, which is specified in BEN-KIKI ET AL. (2009). Like JSON, YAML constitutes a simple format designed with particular focus towards data exchange, but contains

advanced structural components defined as *node styles* (BEN-KIKI ET AL. 2009, Sect. 3.2.3.1). According to BEN-KIKI ET AL. (2009, Sect. 1.3) every document that conforms to JSON is a valid YAML document. The specification introduces *recommended schemata* in BEN-KIKI ET AL. (2009, Sect. 10).

Although the introduced XML, JSON and YAML denote popular formats for the description of semi-structured data, other alternatives such as Comma-separated values (CSV) exist and should be considered for integrative scenarios.

2.2 Data Integration

To allow the combination of heterogeneous data sources, the term interoperability is of particular interest as it describes the capability of systems to interact with each other in a meaningful fashion—thus representing a core requirement of data integration. Integrative approaches are confronted with the problem areas of *distribution, autonomy and heterogeneity*, which LESER & NAUMANN (2007, 50) call the *orthogonal dimensions of information integration*.

Whereas the resolution of physical distribution and autonomy can be an important aspect of integration e.g. in cases where autonomous organizations and systems need to be harmonized, the concept of interoperability assumes a possibly deliberate existence of heterogeneous systems, which are required to interact. Anticipating the discussion of the application domain in chapter 3, the distribution and autonomy of disciplines, organizations and data sources in the arts and humanities are considered as main causes for heterogeneity, but rather reflect the diversity of the domain than present a problem solvable by means of data integration.

LESER & NAUMANN (2007, 60-78) distinguish between *technical, syntactic, data-model, structural, schematic and semantic heterogeneity*, which can be addressed by the classes of *technical and context interoperability*—particularly addressing the two expert groups of computer scientists and domain experts that are involved with the interdisciplinary domain of the digital humanities.

2.2.1 Technical interoperability

The class of technical interoperability has been formed in order to reflect that aspects of heterogeneous syntaxes, encodings, access methods etc. require technological rather than context knowledge for their resolution. Due to the disciplinary separability of the digital humanities, technical interoperability can at least partially be established by applying traditional technological methods of data integration.

Standardized access to data

An often approached initial step towards interoperability is constituted by the implementation of a standardized access protocol, which is—in the context of the arts and humanities (see e.g. [VIERKANT 2013](#))—often found in the [Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting \(OAI-PMH\)](#). The OAI-PMH denotes a standard with the goal to facilitate the technically interoperable data publication and access. The specification identifies the roles of *repositories*—implementing the OAI-PMH as server applications that provide data—and *harvesters*, which are considered as client applications—issuing commands to retrieve metadata from repositories for aggregation ([LAGOZE ET AL. 2002](#), Sect. 2). Table 2.1 shows the available requests that can be used for an interaction in terms of OAI-PMH ([LAGOZE ET AL. 2002](#), Sect. 4).

Figure 2.2 shows an exemplary data integration scenario, which is based on OAI-PMH for the exchange of metadata ([GILL 2008](#), 12-13): Harvesting metadata according to OAI-PMH is based on the request/response (1, 2) principle and is concluded by processing and storing (3) metadata records at the service provider. If available, addresses to described resources can be extracted from the metadata record and requested from the repository. Since these requests are not within the scope of OAI-PMH, the service provider needs to implement a custom harvester with the ability to process provided addresses (4), then request (5), receive (6), process and finally store (7) digital resources. Based on aggregated metadata and resources, integrative services can provide unifying views over the data of distributed repositories (8).

The OAI-PMH specification mandates that repositories present data in simple [Dublin Core Metadata Element Set \(DC\)](#). Whereas additional XML schemata can

Figure 2.2: Metadata Harvesting Model (GILL 2008, 33)

be supported in order to provide metadata in terms of a structure, which suits the context of particular collections, the required implementation of simple DC enables broad views over large sets of collections within aggregating services.

Data and metadata standards

DC is a collection of specifications for the generic, context-independent description of resources fostered by the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative \(DCMI\)](#). The core of the specifications consists of the [Dublin Core Metadata Element Set \(DCES\)](#), a set of 15 elements summarized in table 2.3 (DCMI 2012, Sect. *The Elements*). The core set of elements is extended by the [DCMI Metadata Terms](#)⁷ as well as application specific profiles such as the [Dublin Core Collections Application Profile](#)⁸—allowing the adaption of the DC specification to custom application scenarios. A central characteristic of the DCMI and its specifications thereby consists in a cross-disciplinary focus⁹.

Numerous standards can be identified, which address more specific target communities and respective information needs. An example of a standard dedicated to the publication of academic dissertations and publications can e.g. be found in [XMetaDissPlus](#), a metadata standard of the German National Library. Within language-oriented use-cases, the [Text Encoding Initiative \(TEI\) Guidelines](#) constitute a complex, widely adopted schema for the annotation and description of texts, which has been the base for multiple derivations such as [TEI lite](#), the [Music Encoding Initiative \(MEI\)](#) and [Epigraphic Documents in TEI XML \(EpiDoc\)](#). TEI documents are contain a metadata header, but also include digitized and annotated versions of the resources they describe, such as books or articles. Complex and expressive standards such as [TEI](#) hence often invalidate the distinction between metadata and data. An overview of commonly used standards in the arts and humanities will be presented as part of the context chapter in section 3.2.

⁷ see <http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms/>

⁸ see <http://dublincore.org/groups/collections/collection-application-profile/>

⁹ <http://dublincore.org/about-us/>

<i>Request</i>	<i>Response</i>
<i>Identify</i>	Metadata about the repository such as the name, base URL, implemented protocol version
<i>ListMetadataFormats</i>	Set of identifiers for the metadata formats that are provided by the repository
<i>ListSets</i>	Description of the potentially hierarchic structure of the repository
<i>ListIdentifiers</i>	List of identifiers of contained metadata records
<i>ListRecords</i>	List of metadata records
<i>GetRecord</i>	A particular record according to an identifier specified in the request

Table 2.1: Supported requests in terms of the OAI-PMH

<i>Element</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>contributor</i>	Entity such as a person or organization that contributes to the resource
<i>coverage</i>	Spacial and/or temporal context of the resource
<i>creator</i>	Entity such as a person or organization that creates the resource
<i>date</i>	Any event associated with the resource (creation, modification etc.)
<i>description</i>	Explanation of the resource such as an abstract or table of contents
<i>format</i>	Format of the digital resource, file size, dimensions etc.
<i>identifier</i>	A unique reference to the resource within a particular context (collection)
<i>language</i>	Language of the resource
<i>publisher</i>	Entity such as a person or organization that publishes the resource
<i>relation</i>	Identification of related resources
<i>rights</i>	Rights in and over the resource
<i>source</i>	Reference to an original resource
<i>subject</i>	Topic specified by a keyword, phrase or code
<i>title</i>	Name of the resource
<i>type</i>	Nature or genre of the resource

Table 2.3: Elements of simple DC

2.2.2 Context interoperability

The application of access protocols and standards for the description of data and metadata—in particular the OAI-PMH and XML based standards commonly found

in the arts and humanities—address heterogeneity on several levels, i.e. those of technical, syntactical and datamodel heterogeneity according to the classification in (LESER & NAUMANN 2007, 60-78). The remaining levels can be summarized under the problem area of context interoperability, because the resolution of structural, schematic and semantic heterogeneity depend on the application of background knowledge about the collection and its disciplinary perspective.

Figure 2.3: Value correlations, the mapping and data transformation (based on LESER & NAUMANN 2007, 125)

The process of comparing a source and target schema for the purpose of detecting concepts that are described by both of the compared schemata is called *schema matching*. As such, RAHM defines the aim of schema matching as "identifying semantic correspondences between metadata structures or models, such as database schemas, XML message formats, and ontologies" RAHM (2011, 3). Studies presented by RAHM (2011), FALCONER & NOY (2011) and SHVAIKO & EUZENAT (2013) show that there has been intense research on automated techniques for the support of schema matching in recent years. Developed solutions show limitations when automatically matching complex or large sets of schemata, which is why semi-automatic approaches based on the interaction with domain experts appear beneficial (RAHM 2011, 23-24). SHVAIKO & EUZENAT (2005, 154) present an detailed overview of automated schema matching approaches and show that multiple

classes of techniques can be identified—ranging from simple string-based analyses of element labels to sophisticated approaches including external details such as preexisting mappings or taxonomies.

In order to enable the generation of unifying views over heterogeneous sets of semi-structured data, associations between the elements of schemata need to be aggregated and applied to transform data specified in local schemata to their corresponding representation in terms of the unifying view (target schema). The result of schema matching typically consists in value correlations—loosely associating possibly correlating elements between the schemata, which are aggregated and interpreted by domain experts to generate a mapping. As shown in figure 2.3, mappings correspond to this aggregation and can be considered as an intermediate step in the data integration process.

3

Chapter

Application context

The arts and humanities constitute a branch of academic disciplines, which study human constructs, concerns and culture. Examples of the numerous individual fields range from the language-oriented linguistics, philology and literature over specific facets of history, religious studies and philosophy to the visual and performing arts. The diversity of individual research questions, viewpoints and studied resources results in a high complexity for integrative approaches with a holistic perspective on the arts and humanities.

After an introduction to the characteristics of digital collections in the arts and humanities (section 3.1), research data and especially the commonly utilized schemata for semi-structured data will be addressed (section 3.2). Based on an overview of existing approaches in the fields (section 3.3), the derivation of abstract use-cases for the theoretical concept of this thesis (section 3.4) conclude the chapter.

3.1 Digital collections

Data sources that show relevance for scholarly research are composed of digital versions of traditional archives, libraries and museums as well as collections which only exist in digital forms. Being owned by autonomous institutions, heterogeneity can particularly be found in data models and the context that is required to correctly understand the data. As opposed to the high level of autonomy and distribution, standards such as [OAI-PMH](#) have been established and facilitate access to publicly

available collections.

The 2012 Census of Open Access Repositories in Germany (VIERKANT 2013) provides an evaluation of publicly accessible repositories. The survey restricts the set of relevant data sources with respect to (1) the *geographical localization* to repositories in Germany and (2) the *content coverage* to scientific publications. Open access repositories were examined with respect to the utilized software components, the distribution within Germany, provided metadata formats and functions such as bibliographic export, usage statistics and social features. A significant result of the survey with respect to data integration consists in the conclusion that 141 repositories with a total of 704,121 records on scientific publications were found. 41% of the repositories contained up to 1,000 entries, 33% between 1,000 and 5,000 and 26 % between 5,000 and 50,000 records (VIERKANT 2013, 8-9).

The diagrams in figure 3.1 show the number of registered repositories and harvested records in OAIster, a popular search engine for OAI-PMH accessible records, which was initiated by the University of Michigan in 2002 and has been managed by the Online Computer Library Center (OCLC) since 2009. OAIster is based on an active registration of repositories by contributing organizations. Between the installation in June 2002 and the change of backing organizations in September 2009, the size of OAIster grew to 1,139 registered repositories with over 23 million harvested records—the web-page of OAIster¹⁰ now references over 1,500 contributors and 30 million records.

Comprehensively considering the arts and humanities as context of this thesis, an extensive analysis of possibly relevant data sources is largely prevented by the characteristics of the domain:

- *Autonomous disciplines*: Fields and organizations affiliated to the arts and humanities have no shared authority but operate autonomously. Final conclusions on the relevance of particular collections have to be drawn with respect to individual research questions and educational content. The in-depth knowledge about respective fields is, however, not available on a holistic perspective, but can only be partially answered by domain experts.
- *Number of collections*: The limitation of the set of relevant research questions and hence relevant data sources is not possible as any collection could prove

¹⁰ <http://www.oclc.org/oaister/about.en.html>

Figure 3.1: OAIster statistics between June 2002 and September 2009 (based on UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN 2011)

to be relevant for a particular research question.

3.2 Research data

Digital collections of the arts and humanities contain data that has been accumulated within numerous projects and studies and are as diverse as the disciplines and research questions themselves. Irrespective of the context of a particular resource, the concept of research data consists of three parts:

- *Physical resource*: Objects such as written or printed texts, paintings or musical works, archived in the physical collections of museums, archives etc.
- *Digital resource*: a digital representation of a physical resource such as a scanned version of a book or a digital image of a painting.
- *Descriptions*: semi-structured metadata, that contains information about the physical and/or digital resource such as the title, creator etc.

The landscape of digital collections is characterized by a large set of schemata being used to describe contained resources. Custom data models are often created due to the lack of standards that contain representations of the concepts required by particular collections. However, multiple schemata have evolved as standards for particular domains or as means for overall interoperability between data sources. A widely used specification can be found in simple DC, which has been introduced in section 2.2.1. As the specification refrains from constraints on the contents and

syntax of the elements, DC has a simple structure, but provides largely unspecified elements and can hence be employed as required by individual collections.

Listing 3.1 shows a DC metadata entry in Pangaea, a data publisher for earth and environmental science. Although not a digital collection of the arts and humanities, there is a potential relevance of such *external* data especially for fields that include the analysis of environmental and material data such as archeology, art history or Jewish studies.

```
<oai_dc:dc xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:xsi="http://
www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:oai_dc="http://www.
openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.
openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/ http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/
oai_dc.xsd">
<dc:title>Sedimentology and susceptibility of core MD88–769</dc:title>
<dc:creator>Bareille, Gilles F</dc:creator>
<dc:creator>Grousset, Francis E</dc:creator>
<dc:creator>Labracherie, Monique</dc:creator>
<dc:creator>Labeyrie, Laurent D</dc:creator>
<dc:creator>Petit, Jean–Robert</dc:creator>
<dc:publisher>PANGAEA</dc:publisher>
<dc:date>1994–03–17</dc:date>
<dc:type>Dataset</dc:type>
<dc:format>text/tab-separated-values, 1064 data points</dc:format>
<dc:identifier>http://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.51915
</dc:identifier>
<dc:identifier>doi:10.1594/PANGAEA.51915</dc:identifier>
<dc:language>en</dc:language>
<dc:rights>CC–BY: Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported</dc:rights>
<dc:rights>Access constraints: unrestricted</dc:rights>
<dc:relation>doi:10.1594/PANGAEA.733896</dc:relation>
<dc:relation>Bareille, Gilles F; Grousset, Francis E; Labracherie,
Monique; Labeyrie, Laurent D; Petit, Jean–Robert (1994): Origin of
detrital fluxes in the southeast Indian Ocean during the last
climatic cycles. Paleoclimatology, 9(6), 799–820, doi:10.1029/94
PA01946</dc:relation>
<dc:coverage>LATITUDE: –46.069333 * LONGITUDE: 90.111167 * MINIMUM AGE:
4.610 ka BP * MAXIMUM AGE: 201.000 ka BP * MINIMUM DEPTH, sediment/
rock: 0.0 m * MAXIMUM DEPTH, sediment/rock: 11.7 m</dc:coverage>
<dc:subject>Accumulation rate, terrigenous; APSARA4; Density, dry bulk;
Detritus; Feldspar flux; Marion Dufresne; MD88–769; Piston corer;
Quartz; Quartz flux; Sedimentation rate; South Pacific;
Susceptibility; Susceptibility flux</dc:subject>
</oai_dc:dc>
```

Listing 3.1: DC document with composed elements¹¹

¹¹ http://ws.pangaea.de/oai/?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_dc&identifier=oai:pangaea.de:doi:10.1594/PANGAEA.51915

Whereas the data of the presented example conforms to the specifications of the standard, the especially the coverage element displays an inclusion of collection-specific data within a generic metadata standard. Although counterintuitive from a database modeling perspective, the aggregation of multiple atomic values within the domain of one element results in a context-oriented customization of a generic schema—increasing the semantic content of the records. Please note that although Pangaea provides data in terms of specific metadata schemata, the representation in DC is of particular relevance for interoperability considerations, which become especially important if unifying views over collections from different disciplinary backgrounds are generated. The 2012 Census of Open Access Repositories in Germany confirm this assumption by entitling simple DC as the only metadata format, which deserves the label of a *standard*. (VIERKANT 2013, 21)

POLFREMAN (2005) presents a set of metadata standards that have been commonly found in documents collected by the Arts and Humanities Data Service (AHDS), a service that focused on the collection, preservation and promotion of digital research data of the arts and humanities—particularly archaeology, history, literature, language and linguistics as well as the visual and performing arts. The list includes formats such as DC, Machine Readable Cataloguing (MARC) and Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS), which can be summarized as generic, discipline- and resource-type agnostic metadata standards, as well as specifications such as Categories for the Description of Works of Art (CDWA), TEI header and Visual Resources Association (VRA) core, which have originated from information and research needs within the arts and humanities. As an example of a widely used standard, the TEI header represents guidelines for the description and annotation of texts and is utilized especially in the context of digital libraries. The TEI header has been customized by multiple profiles and derivations such as TEI lite, MEI and EpiDoc, which have been adopted in their respective fields. The TEI guidelines can be considered as possible integrative standard for digital resources in language oriented contexts. In contrast to generic schemata, specific standards such as TEI foster the consideration of specific details of respective domains. The mentioned CDWA and VRA core constitute examples for possible integrative standards in other parts of the arts and humanities—both providing elements for the description of works of art or museum objects (POLFREMAN 2005).

```

<datei xmlns="http://www.ddb.de/professionell/mabxml/mabxml-1.xsd"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.ddb.de/professionell/mabxml/mabxml-1.xsd
    http://www.ddb.de/professionell/mabxml/mabxml-1.xsd">
  <datensatz id="ID946451494" typ="h" status="n" mabVersion="M2.0">
    <feld nr="001" ind=" " >946451494</feld>
    <feld nr="004" ind=" " >19980605</feld>
    <feld nr="030" ind=" " >a|i a r |z |||37</feld>
    <feld nr="036" ind="a" >DE</feld>
    <feld nr="050" ind=" " >a|a |||||</feld>
    <feld nr="051" ind=" " >m|||z ||</feld>
    <feld nr="070" ind="a" >292</feld>
    <feld nr="100" ind="b" >Ginsbach , Julia</feld>
    <feld nr="102" ind="a" >11547577X</feld>
    <feld nr="104" ind="b" >Liebers , Andrea</feld>
    <feld nr="106" ind="a" >111570204</feld>
    <feld nr="331" ind=" " ><ns>Die</ns> schöne Lau</feld>
    <feld nr="335" ind=" " >nach dem Stuttgarter Hutzelmännlein von Eduart M
      örike</feld>
    <feld nr="359" ind=" " >Julia Ginsbach (Bilder) ; Andrea Liebers (Text)
      </feld>
    <feld nr="410" ind=" " >Leinfelden–Echterdingen</feld>
    <feld nr="412" ind=" " >DRW–Verl. Weinbrenner</feld>
    <feld nr="425" ind=" " >1995</feld>
    <feld nr="425" ind="a" >1995</feld>
    <feld nr="433" ind=" " >[28] S.</feld>
    <feld nr="434" ind=" " >Überw. III.</feld>
    <feld nr="435" ind=" " >27 cm</feld>
    <feld nr="540" ind="a" >ISBN 3–87181–371–0 Pp. : DM 24.80</feld>
    <feld nr="544" ind="a" >DBL<tf/>1996 B 2108</feld>
    <feld nr="544" ind="a" >DBF<tf/>1996 B 2108</feld>
    <feld nr="574" ind=" " >96,A07,0146</feld>
    <feld nr="700" ind=" " >|07</feld>
    <feld nr="800" ind=" " >118583107 Mörike , Eduard</feld>
    <feld nr="805" ind="b" ><ns>Das</ns> Stuttgarter Hutzelmännchen</feld>
  </datensatz>
</datei>

```

Listing 3.2: Example document that conforms to the MABxml schema¹²

Despite the differences concerning appropriate application domains and the level of granularity, most schemata are comprised of elements that are created and labeled with respect to the concepts they represent. Listing 3.2 shows an exemplary document that conforms to the MABxml specification (KETT 2005)—an XML-based data exchange format for libraries. Any property of a particular record is represented by a field element—the semantic association of the element

¹² http://files.dnb.de/standards/formate/mabxml_beispiel_ebene1.xml

is determined by the *nr* attribute.

3.3 Applications

The research data landscape of the arts and humanities is characterized by a high heterogeneity of digital collections and the used schemata. In conjunction with the diversity of individual fields and hence the research questions and methodologies, this landscape leads to a central implication for the construction of data integration approaches: The selection of an appropriate global schema for creating integrative views depends on knowledge about the relevant set of collections as well as the information needs of a particular target community.

As a consequence, *specific solutions* have been created in order to create integrated views, which focus on particular research questions or disciplines. An example can be found in the search *Vieles Finden*¹³ of the Salomon Ludwig Steinheim-Institut: Focusing on collections with data of particular relevance for studies of German-Jewish history, the search aggregates data from heterogeneous and distributed sources for a particular scholarly community.

Aside from such specific projects, there is a discernible trend towards the development and installation of infrastructures, which indicates the interest in *interdisciplinary projects*. Examples can be found in the European initiatives¹⁴ of Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) and Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) as well as established services of OAIster (see HAGEDORN 2003) and Europeana (see PERONI ET AL. 2013): Extending the considered application domain, the initiatives share the common goal of creating integrative services over large sets of data sources. DARIAH thus considers the arts and humanities, CLARIN focuses on language-oriented disciplines, OAIster integrates any OAI-PMH endpoint that is registered and Europeana focuses on selected digital resources such as "manuscripts, documents, paintings, art and architecture objects, photos, videos etc." (PERONI ET AL. 2013, 229).

In general, the two opposing strategies of *horizontal* and *vertical integration* as indicated in figure 3.2 can be identified as means to reduce the complexity resulting

¹³ see http://www.steinheim-institut.de/wiki/index.php/Vieles_finden

¹⁴ a recent overview of current EU initiatives is presented by DASISH (2013, 18-19)

from the high number of heterogeneous disciplines, collections and schemata in the context of the arts and humanities:

- *Horizontal integration*: A large set of heterogeneous data sources is integrated, which results in a limited conceptual overlap between the considered collections and hence the utilization of a generic global schema.
- *Vertical integration*: A specific focus on the information needs of research questions, disciplines or communities increases the intersection of the concepts addressed in the collections and allows the definition of more specific integrative models. Please note that the dimension of the considered domain is rather exemplary and could be replaced by other factors that define the overall semantic similarity of the set of collections, such as the resource types in the case of Europeana.

Figure 3.2: Horizontal and vertical integration strategies

Although presented as orthogonal forms of data integration in figure 3.2, the strategies are not easily distinguishable in practice. Approaches to data integration can, however, be classified according to the characteristics of the integration strategies: the search of the Salomon Ludwig Steinheim-Institut e.g. concentrates on one specific field and hence provides a rather vertical service. CLARIN considers language-oriented resources addressing a set of semantically overlapping disci-

plines, which allows a deeper integration granularity compared to OAIster, which provides a broad, discipline-agnostic view over multiple, semantically unrelated collections.

3.4 Summary and use-cases

The purpose of this chapter consisted in the introduction of those aspects of the research data landscape of the arts and humanities, which are particularly relevant for the construction of a data integration strategy. Abstract use-cases for a generic data integration concept can be derived—based on the discussion of digital collections, the contained research data and existing integrative approaches:

Section 3.1 indicated the existence of a large amount of data sources, which contain resources of potential relevance for the arts and humanities. The collections show a high degree of distribution, autonomy and semantic heterogeneity, but often provide standardized access in terms of OAI-PMH. Neither the composition nor the volatility of the set of relevant collections can be a priori determined, mainly because the concept of *relevance* depends on information needs of particular research questions within their distinct disciplinary context.

Section 3.2 showed that published descriptions and—in the case of more expressive standards such as TEI—resources typically follow semi-structured data models mostly formalized in terms of XML schemata. With the application of semi-structured data models, technical aspects of interoperability are facilitated. Especially since the models expose different levels of complexity and address distinct academic disciplines, interoperability problems that require the explication of domain knowledge remain open. This effect is intensified by the existence of data models, whose interpretation depends on their utilization in particular collections (e.g. MabXML) as well as coarse standards (e.g. DC), which are often detailed in a collection-specific fashion.

Section 3.3 highlighted the opposing horizontal and vertical strategies that are currently being applied to reduce the complexity of data integration in the arts and humanities. Approaches following any of the strategies are typically based on the creation or selection of a global schema in order to provide a unifying view on heterogeneous data. Schemata for a deep semantic integration include the

Figure 3.3: Overview on important use-case types

specific concepts interesting to a particular community or discipline, whereas broad schemata unify a larger set of heterogeneous collections and local schemata and are thus often represented by a simple, generically reusable schema such as DC.

The construction of the generic integration model in this paper involves the combination of horizontal and vertical integration, which should be dynamically adaptable to individual information needs. Figure 3.3 shows four abstract use-cases of implementing services, which illustrate requirements to the generic integration model.

- *Broad Search (Use-Case 1)*: Users aim to identify relevant collections and resources within a large set of collections.
- *Make searchable (Use-Case 2)*: Organizations or researchers with relevant data with an aim to contribute their data to a greater public.
- *Data integration (Use-Case 3)*: Data integration use-cases such as data migration or consolidation can involve small to large sets of collections; a suitable unifying view should be selected accordingly.
- *Deep search (Use-Case 4)*: An expert search specifically designated to particular communities and disciplines that is based on an integrative view that contains relevant concepts.

4

Chapter

Concept

As indicated in section 3.2, the set of commonly used formats in the arts and humanities includes numerous schemata, which have been developed with respect to the requirements of particular application information needs or in order to facilitate interoperability among heterogeneous sources. Although the publication formats of digital collections in the arts and humanities are assumed to be based mainly on XML, a theoretical perspective on schemata and mappings facilitates the definition of a generic integration model on a technology-independent level and the associated benefits:

- *Extensibility* of the model with respect to different formats such as XML, JSON and CSV.
- *Differentiation* of technical and domain-oriented aspects of data integration and thus the identification of tasks resolvable by the groups of computing and domain experts.

Based on the introduction of the application domain and the identified requirements, section 4.1 introduces initial conclusions and presents a fundamental conceptual architecture. Section 4.2 then differentiates the considered modeling layers and basic formal terminology before the sections 4.3 and 4.4 present a theoretical specification of schemata and mapping. Identified issues with respect mainly to the scalability of the integration model are addressed by section 4.5, which concludes the conceptual work of this thesis.

4.1 Conceptual architecture

LENZERINI (2002, 233-234) characterizes a fundamental architecture for data integration systems based on a global schema, a set of source schemata and mappings which are composed with respect to the goal of presenting an integrated view over multiple heterogeneous data sources.

- The *global schema* represents the unified view.
- A set of *source schemata* describe the structural layout of source data.
- *Mappings* consist of correlations between the elements of a source schema and its equivalent elements in the global schema.

Approaches to data integration are often based on this architecture and examples in the context of the arts and humanities can be found in the services of Europeana and OAIster, which were briefly introduced in section 3.3. Both Europeana and OAIster provide users with sophisticated services based on the integrated view of a global schema, which is—the in the case of Europeana—"based on the DCMI Metadata Terms and a number of more advanced metadata models" (PERONI ET AL. 2013, 228) and—in the case of OAIster—primarily built on a transformed version of simple DC (HAGEDORN 2003, 172-174).

A characteristic of the design process of integrative approaches according to LENZERINI consists in an extensive requirements analysis, which—among other functional and non-functional requirements—results in the collection of the concepts addressed by relevant local schemata and the derivation of a global schema. To assess the suitability of such a global schema, the goals of schema integration according to BATINI ET AL. (1986, 337) can be applied, but need to be adapted to consider the aspect of relevance:

- *Completeness*: A global schema needs to include all concepts addressed within integrated schemata, which are relevant for a considered target-community or goal.
- *Correctness*: Any concept described by a local schema must exist in a semantically equivalent form within the global schema.
- *Minimality*: Semantically equal concepts may only be represented once within the integrated schema.
- *Understandability*: The global schema must be understandable for developers,

designers and users—names of elements and attribute should be labeled similar to their original representations.

The restriction of the completeness requirement to include only the set of relevant concepts is essential in order to prevent the inclusion of elements of missing significance, which unnecessarily increases the complexity of the global schema: As OAIster constitutes a service with the goal to integrate numerous distributed and highly heterogeneous data sources, a relatively flat global schema has been chosen and provides a "common denominator" of the sources. Europeana is limiting the heterogeneity of data sources by focusing on "museums, archives, audiovisual collections and libraries" (PERONI ET AL. 2013, 229), which increases the set of relevant elements—thus resulting in a more expressive and complex global schema.

Conclusions

The primary issue for the conception of a suitable integration architecture in this thesis can be inferred from the defined application context, which consists in the whole spectrum of the arts and humanities: By respecting use-cases that integrate a large set of collections as well as integrative scenarios that focus on specific information needs and a limited set of collections, the static definition of a global schema as an intersection of relevant elements of the considered data sources is not possible.

With respect to the requirements on global schemata adapted from BATINI ET AL. and additional requirements expressed in section 3.4 the conceptual architecture is based on the following hypotheses:

1. There is no definable global schema, which satisfies requirements of completeness, correctness, minimality, understandability and relevance for the application domain of the arts and humanities with respect to the considered integration use-cases.
2. Integrative views can be determined by respective domain experts based on information needs that correlate e.g. with particular research questions, use-cases or disciplines.
3. Based on an abstraction from technical aspects of heterogeneity the integration of data sources can be facilitated, which incites research projects and

Figure 4.1: Associated clusters form a reusable base of mappings

domain experts to utilize the capabilities to express background knowledge in the form of schema definition and semantic mappings.

4. An interconnection of determined or continuously emerging integrative schemata enables the ad-hoc generation of broader views over previously unrelated schemata and hence digital collections

Figure 4.1 provides a schematic visualization of the architecture based on these assumptions: The semantic clusters should be interpreted as results of research projects that provide details about schemata and their correlations. Based on the coherence, groups of tightly correlated schemata can be identified along with schemata that were selected or qualify as integrative schemata (*S3*, *S5*, *S8*) for the clusters. By associating these integrative schemata, clusters can be extended—potentially allowing broad or interdisciplinary views. By connecting *S3*, *S5* and *S8* with a schema that is focused on interoperability *S10*, global views can be created.

4.2 Formal foundation

Approaches to formalize schemata e.g. in the field of schema matching and mapping are often implicitly or explicitly based on XML, but define schema in a more abstract sense—thereby aiming at a theoretical perspective.

Such formal definitions are presented e.g. by SUCIU (2009) and ZHANG ET AL. (2005): "A semi-structured data instance is a rooted, directed graph in which the edges carry labels representing schema components, and leaf nodes (i.e., nodes without any outgoing edges) are labeled with data values (integers, reals, strings, etc.)" (SUCIU 2009, 2601). ZHANG ET AL. understand a schema as a structure with matching

objects, labels, labeling functions and relations (ZHANG ET AL. 2005, 695). The definition of schema matching as "identifying semantic correspondences between metadata structures or models, such as database schemas, XML message formats, and ontologies" (RAHM 2011, 3) presents a broad interpretation by relating the term schema to the concepts of metadata structure and model. In general, a schema specifies the structure of data—as in the case of XML in terms of constraints on elements, attributes and relationships (MURATA ET AL. 2005, 661). The interpretation of the term is often focused on XML due to its widespread usage for storing and exchanging semi-structured data (see e.g. MURATA ET AL. 2005) and apply the term to XML schemata with respect to the W3C XML Schema specification (THOMPSON ET AL. 2012).

The conceptual understanding of schemata and schema languages in this thesis is based on the four layer modeling architecture, which originated from the Model-driven architecture (MDA). Although an approach to software engineering as discussed in BÉZIVIN (2005) and ATKINSON & KÜHNE (2003), the architecture is applicable for the formalization of semi-structured data as shown in figure 4.2.

MDA focuses on the development of platform-independent models and their incremental transformation to implementation-oriented models and software components. As such, the layer $M0$ contains an operational system and the levels $M1$ - $M3$ are considered as modeling layers, which each specify the syntax and semantics of the respective underlying layer. The Unified Modelling Language (UML) and Meta Object Facility (MOF) are widely used in the context of software engineering: UML diagrams on layer $M1$ present a domain-oriented view on the state and behavior of a particular system in terms of static and dynamic models. Individual UML diagrams follow the syntactical and semantic specification of the UML ($M2$), which is itself formally defined in terms of the MOF ($M3$).

Transferred to the context of data formalization, a data model or schema is interpreted as a language specifying the structure and behavior of a the data within a system: Semi-structured data e.g. in XML documents ($M0$) describe the data-layer of a system, which is modeled in terms of schemata ($M1$)—containing the syntactical and semantic constraints on data. A schema such as a Document Type Definition (DTD) or an XML schema is defined in terms of a schema language ($M2$), which needs to conform to the basic constraints of semi-structured data ($M0$)

Figure 4.2: Four layer modeling architecture (based on BÉZIVIN 2005, 178; ATKINSON & KÜHNE 2003, 38)

and hence needs to expose a "graph- or tree-like structure" (BUNEMAN 1997, 118). A schema language defines constraints on schemata, defining both syntactical (alphabet) and semantic (constraints and relation of the alphabet) aspects.

4.3 Schemata metamodeling

Schemata are domain-oriented specifications of the constraints of structured and semi-structured data. As such, they define representations of concepts and their properties as required by particular information needs, e.g. of an academic community or an integrative view. With respect to semi-structured data, schemata can be inherently defined such as in XML documents without referenced XML schemata or embedded DTD. Based on the discussion of the characteristics of digital collections in the arts and humanities in section 3.1, a structural consistency of delimitable sets of documents is inferred, which can be utilized for schema integration.

The objective of this section consists in the definition of a generic schema

language that allows the format-independent description of schemata and thus facilitates their semantic interrelation by abstracting from technical aspects of heterogeneity. The theoretical perspective on schemata as applied in this section builds mainly on the work of ZHANG ET AL. (2005) and MURATA ET AL. (2005):

Based on the problem of semi-automatic schema matching, ZHANG ET AL. present an algebraic framework for the purpose of describing schemata as well as schema matching from a formal perspective. Eventually leading to the key finding of the paper, which consists in the classification of schema matching as a problem of graph homomorphism (ZHANG ET AL. 2005, 695-697), a formal definition of a schema can be adapted in terms of a finite structure $S = \langle E, L, F, R \rangle$, where:

- E forms the finite set of elements, which are matched with their semantic equivalents in other schemata,
- L is a set of string labels,
- F is a set of labeling functions that assign labels to elements and
- R represents the set of relations between the elements of the schema.

The definition of ZHANG ET AL. is intentionally generic in order to be applicable to object-oriented, structured and semi-structured models. By restricting the available types of relations R accordingly, the definition conforms to the unifying understanding of semi-structured data as a directed, labeled graph or tree (see e.g. ABITEBOUL 2009, 2599; SUCIU 2009, 2601; BUNEMAN 1997, 118), where the set of L -labeled nodes are represented by E and the set of edges are defined over R .

Along with the classification and comparison of XML schema languages, MURATA ET AL. provide another formal perspective on schemata, which is based on language theory. Applying the concept of regular tree languages, they describe a schema as an ordered, node-labeled¹⁵ tree without fixed arities¹⁶ (MURATA ET AL. 2005, 663). A regular tree grammar is defined as quadruple $G = \langle N, T, S, P \rangle$, where N are non-terminal and T are terminal symbols, $S \subseteq N$ constitutes the start-symbol and P defines a set of production rules (MURATA ET AL. 2005, 663-665).

Based on a combination of the matching-oriented perspective in ZHANG ET AL. and the foundation of regular tree grammars as presented by MURATA ET AL., the formal definition of schema is derived as:

¹⁵ excluding leaves (text-nodes), which are labeled by the instance values

¹⁶ a node can potentially have any number of child nodes

Definition 4.1 *A schema describes a regular tree grammar and is defined in terms of a 6-tuple $S = \langle N, T, R, P, E, F \rangle$, where N, T, R and P form the static, grammatical components:*

- N is the set of uniquely identifiable non-terminal symbols.
- T describes the set of terminal symbols.
- $R \in N$ constitutes the root symbol.
- P is a set of production rules $n \rightarrow te_c$, where $n \in N, t \in T$ and e_c represents the content model defined over the set of non-terminal symbols.

L and F provide a semantic extension upon the predefined, static structure of the schema, where

- L constitutes a set of uniquely identifiable labels and
- F is a set of functions of the form $x \rightarrow le_l$, where:
 - $x \in (N \cup L)$,
 - $l \in L$ and
 - an expression $e_l := \{I, op\}$ defined over a set of input values $I \subseteq (N \cup x)$ and an operation of the arity $|I|$.

The interpretation of a schema according to definition 4.1 combines two distinctive aspects, which are considered fundamental for a semantically enriched representation of schemata with respect to the defined use-cases of the arts and humanities.

4.3.1 Static structure

The components N, T, R and P describe the *static, grammatical structure* of a schema, which is required for the validation and processing of semi-structured data. Based on the foundation by MURATA ET AL. (2005, 662-666), the conceptual relationship between a schema—in the sense of a generative grammar—and a corresponding schema language can be detailed as follows:

Definition 4.2 *A schema specifies a grammar for the generation of semi-structured documents. The finite and complete set of documents that can be generated by the schema constitutes the particular schema language conforming to that schema.*

The alphabet of a schema language is formed by the set of terminals T —defining the symbols usable to compose the nodes of conforming document trees. While

being central for the execution of production rules, non-terminal symbols N are not part of the language, but utilized in intermediate steps of the grammar: Starting at the root symbol R , appropriate production rules $p \in P$ are applied to non-terminals—replacing them with terminal symbols until a tree of terminals remains. Table 4.1 shows the grammatical components of a schema, which generates a language that includes the document in listing 4.1. Please note that parts of the document, i.e. the header, namespace declarations and some elements were omitted. The full and unmodified version can be obtained through the OAI-PMH interface of Propylaeum-DOK¹⁷, a publication platform for ancient studies at the University of Heidelberg. The original document conforms to the XMetaDissPlus specification¹⁸.

```
<xmd:xMetaDiss>
  <dc:title xsi:type="ddb:titleISO639-2" lang="ger">Hauranite sculpture</dc:
    title>
  <dc:creator xsi:type="pc:MetaPers">
    <pc:person>
      <pc:name type="nameUsedByThePerson">
        <pc:foreName>Robert</pc:foreName>
        <pc:surName>Wenning</pc:surName>
      </pc:name>
    </pc:person>
  </dc:creator>
  <dc:subject xsi:type="xMetaDiss:DDC-SG">730</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject xsi:type="xMetaDiss:SWD">Kunstmuseum</dc:subject>
  <dc:subject xsi:type="xMetaDiss:SWD">Sammlung</dc:subject>
  <dc:identifier xsi:type="urn:nbn">urn:nbn:de:bsz:16-propylaeumdok-8539</
    dc:identifier>
  <ddb:contact ddb:contactID="F6000-0201"/>
  <ddb:identifier ddb:type="URL">http://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/
    propylaeumdok/853/</ddb:identifier>
</xMetaDiss:xMetaDiss>
```

Listing 4.1: Example of an XML document specified in terms of XMetaDissPlus

Leaf nodes are indicated by placeholders $\vartheta \in N$ and $\theta \in T$, which are replaced by values of the instances. Following the definition in MURATA ET AL. (2005, 663), ϵ denotes a null sequence of nonterminals in the content model, indicating that no further decomposition is possible.

¹⁷ <http://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/propylaeumdok/cgi/oai2?verb=GetRecord&identifier=oai:propylaeumdok.uni-hd.de:853&metadataPrefix=XMetaDissPlus>, last verified 2013-12-19

¹⁸ <http://files.dnb.de/standards/xmetadissplus/xmetadissplus.xsd>, last verified 2013-12-19

N	$= \{XMetaDiss, Title, Type1, Lang, Creator, Person, Name, Type3, ForeName, SurName, Subject, Identifier1, Contact, ContactID, Identifier2, Type2, \vartheta, \epsilon\}$
T	$= \{xmd : xMetaDiss, dc : title, dc : type, lang, dc : creator, pc : person, pc : name, type, pc : foreName, pc : surName, dc : subject, dc : identifier, ddb : contact, ddb : contactID, ddb : identifier, ddb : type, \theta\}$
R	$= \{XMetaDiss\}$
P	$= \{XMetaDiss \rightarrow xmd : xMetaDiss(Title, Creator, Subject^*, Identifier1, Contact, Identifier2),$ $Title \rightarrow dc : title(Type1, Lang, \vartheta),$ $Type1 \rightarrow xsi : type(\vartheta),$ $Lang \rightarrow lang(\vartheta),$ $Creator \rightarrow dc : creator(Type1, Person),$ $Person \rightarrow pc : person(Name),$ $Name \rightarrow pc : name(Type3, ForeName, SurName),$ $Type3 \rightarrow type(\vartheta),$ $ForeName \rightarrow pc : foreName(\vartheta),$ $SurName \rightarrow pc : surName(\vartheta),$ $Subject \rightarrow dc : subject(Type1, \vartheta)$ $Identifier1 \rightarrow dc : identifier(Type1, \vartheta)$ $Contact \rightarrow ddb : contact(ContactID)$ $ContactID \rightarrow @ddb : contactID(\vartheta),$ $Identifier2 \rightarrow ddb : identifier(Type2, \vartheta)$ $Type2 \rightarrow ddb : type(\vartheta),$ $\vartheta \rightarrow \theta(\epsilon)\}$

Table 4.1: Grammatical components of a schema that generates the document in listing 4.1

Based on MURATA ET AL. (2005, 664) the definition of an interpretation can be derived as:

Definition 4.3 *The interpretation I of a tree T of semi-structured data against a schema S consists in the mapping of each element $e \in T$ to a non-terminal symbol $I(e) \in N$. The tree t is valid against S , if there exists a production rule for each node $e \in T$, which has $I(e)$ on the left and e on the right-hand-side and for the root element of t , the mapped non-terminal is $I(e) \in S$.*

A document tree is considered valid against a schema, if there exists an *interpretation* of that tree that conforms to the schema. Figure 4.3 visualizes both the tree

Figure 4.3: Tree of the XML document in listing 4.1 and its interpretation against the schema in table 4.1

and interpretation of the document in listing 4.1 against the schema in table 4.1 and thereby indicates the validity of the document.

From an integrative perspective, the grammatical components of a schema describe a structure, which is *static* in the sense that it is predetermined by particular communities, organizations or standards bodies. Research data provided by digital collections conforms to such constraints and an integrative system is required to process data accordingly. In consequence, the static aspect of a schema represents a *parsing-oriented view*.

4.3.2 Semantic extension

The sets of labels L and labeling functions F denote an extension to the static structure of a schema according to definition 4.1—adding the capability to include details about the structure and content of semi-structured data, which are not

inherently available in external schemata and as such not addressable by the schema grammar. As a logical addition to the grammatical constraints, labels are not required for the validation and processing of data as obtained from external sources. The creation of labels and labeling functions depends on the explication of knowledge about context-specific interpretations of particular schemata. The initial specifications of L and F in definition 4.1 lead to enriched information available on a schema:

Definition 4.4 A label $l \in L$ defines a subordinate element of a parent $x \in (N \cup L)$ to which it is assigned by a labeling function of the form $x \rightarrow le_l$. To prevent the introduction of cycles, a label l is only allowed to be used in the right side of one labeling function. Resulting from the defined domain and co-domain of labeling functions, structural sub-trees can be modeled, where:

- a root node $x_r \in N$ is selected from the set of non-terminal symbols,
- any subsequent node $x \neq x_r$ is a label and
- edges are constituted by a function $f \in F$.

A labeling function $x \rightarrow le_l$ associates an element $x \in (N \cup L)$ to a label $l \in N$ —defining l as subordinate element of x . The expression e_l , which is defined by a set of input elements I and an operation, which accepts the number of elements in I . Circles in the resulting tree layout are prevented by definition 4.4. However, in order to prevent circular dependencies within the expressions of labeling functions, the set of available input elements I of an expression e_l in $x_i \rightarrow l_k e_x$ may be composed of

- any non-terminal symbol $n \in N$ and
- superior nodes of l_k .

Considering the exemplary XML document based on DC in listing 4.2, which—assuming a certain consistency within a hosting digital collection—can be modeled in a semantically enriched form based on the labeling extension and the schema of DC in terms of definition 4.1:

- The non-terminal symbol *Creator* contains a full person name, which can be decomposed.
- Based on the assumption that the collection uses a controlled vocabulary for *Type*, the *Creator* could be labeled as *Author* to better reflect to relation

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<dc xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:dc="http://
  purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" >
  <dc:title>For Whom the Bell Tolls</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Hemingway, Ernest</dc:creator>
  <dc:type>Book</dc:type>
  <dc:coverage>Geographical: Spain; Temporal: 1937</dc:coverage>
</dc>
```

Listing 4.2: Simple document based on DC

$L = \{Author, LastName, FirstName, Geographical, Temporal\}$
$F = \{Creator \rightarrow Author(I = \{Type, Creator\}, f_1 := passAuthor(I)),$ $Author \rightarrow LastName(I = \{Author\}, f_2 := stringBefore(", ", I)),$ $Author \rightarrow FirstName(I = \{Author\}, f_3 := stringAfter(", ", I)),$ $Coverage \rightarrow Geographical(I = \{Author\},$ $f_4 := getValueForKey(";", ":", "Geographical", I)),$ $Coverage \rightarrow Temporal(I = \{Author\},$ $f_5 := getValueForKey(";", ":", "Temporal", I))\}$

Table 4.2: Labels and labeling functions for the document in listing 4.2

between the resource and its creator.

- The *Coverage* element contains a substructure, which can be decomposed.

The customized version of DC in terms of the example does not require modifications to N , T , R and P as the grammatical rules are not assumed to be affected by the customization. In case the records published by such a collection are consistently restricted to *dc*, *dc:title*, *dc:creator*, *dc:type* and *dc:coverage*, these constraints could, however, be reflected within the grammatical components. Table 4.2 shows the sets of L and F representing the changes compared to the schema definition of DC, listing 4.3 shows simple Java-oriented methods to complete the example.

The primary benefit of the labeling concept consists in possible semantic extension of a schema, which preserves the original structure and data and—as the labels are modeled as named components of the schema—allows an enrichment of individual schemata being an input to schema matching and mapping.

```
String passAuthor(Element[] input) {
    if (input[0].value.equals("Book")) {
        return input[1].value;
    } else {
        return null;
    }
}

String stringBefore(String delimiter, Element input) {
    return input.value.substring(0, input.value.indexOf(delimiter)).trim();
}

String stringAfter(String delimiter, Element input) {
    return input.value.substring(input.value.indexOf(delimiter)+1).trim();
}

String getValueForKey(String tokenDelimiter, String keyValueDelimiter,
    String key, Element input) {
    StringTokenizer tokenizer = new StringTokenizer(input.value,
        tokenDelimiter);
    String token, possibleKey;

    while (tokenizer.hasMoreTokens()) {
        token = tokenizer.nextToken();
        possibleKey = token.substring(0, token.indexOf(keyValueDelimiter)).trim
            ();
        if (possibleKey.equals(key)) {
            return token.substring(token.indexOf(keyValueDelimiter)+1).trim();
        }
    }
    return null;
}
```

Listing 4.3: Java-oriented operations for the labeling extension specified in table 4.2

4.4 Interrelation of schemata

With the help of the introduced metamodel, schemata for semi-structured data are described in terms of generic grammars. Based on the technology-independent, theoretical view on schemata, modeling tasks of data integration can be classified by means of the four layer modeling architecture (see figure 4.2):

- *Metamodel integration (M2)*: Generic schema languages need to be mapped with the generic language of this thesis to facilitate processing of data in practice. While non-terminal symbols are a logical concept of grammars, terminal symbols and the applicability of production rules depend on specific formats: As XML for example distinguishes between attributes and elements, the incorporation of XML and e.g. JSON into a common grammar requires multiple sets of terminal symbols and production rules.
- *Model integration (M1)*: Schemata are domain-oriented data models, which need to be semantically associated to facilitate the creation of unifying logical views on heterogeneous data. The main focus of model integration consists in the identification and modeling of semantic correspondences.

4.4.1 Metamodel integration

With the definition of a schema as a regular tree grammar, the integration model of this thesis is based on a generic schema language, which allows a format-independent specification of semi-structured data models. An effect for a practical adoption consists in the necessity to relate the internal, generic schema language with format-dependent variants defined e.g. by the W3C XML Schema or JSON Schema.

The introduced schema grammar conforms to the constraints of semi-structured data—formally defined by regular tree grammars capable of representing a directed, labeled tree (see MURATA ET AL. 2005, 662-663; ABITEBOUL 2009, 2599; SUCIU 2009, 2601; BUNEMAN 1997, 118). As such, based on a consistent set of non-terminal symbols N and a defined root symbol $R \in N$, the terminal symbols T and production rules P need to be adapted to conform to the languages of specific formats. For practical implementations, the terminal symbols can be realized in wrappers (compare mediator-based information systems in LESER & NAUMANN 2007, 97-101)—

independent of specific grammars and thereby facilitating the separated resolution of technical and knowledge-based heterogeneity as introduced in section 2.2.

<pre> <resource> <title>A Midsummer Night's Dream</title> <author firstName="William" lastName="Shakespeare"> </author> <authored>1590–1596</authored> <type>play</type> <type>comedy</type> <mainCharacters> <mainCharacter>Duke of Athens</mainCharacter> <mainCharacter>Theseus </mainCharacter> <mainCharacter>Hippolyta </mainCharacter> </mainCharacters> </resource> </pre>	$ \begin{aligned} N &= \{Resource, Title, Author, FName, \\ &\quad LName, Authored, Types, Type \\ &\quad MainCharacters, MainCharacter, \\ &\quad \varnothing, \epsilon\} \\ R &= \{Resource\} \\ T_1 &= \{resource, title, author, @firstName, \\ &\quad @lastName, authored, type, \\ &\quad mainCharacters, mainCharacter, \theta\} \\ P_1 &= \{Resource \rightarrow resource(Title, Author, \\ &\quad Authored, Type^*, MainCharacters), \\ &\quad Title \rightarrow title(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Author \rightarrow author(FName, LName), \\ &\quad FName \rightarrow @firstName(\varnothing), \\ &\quad LName \rightarrow @lastName(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Authored \rightarrow authored(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Type \rightarrow type(\varnothing), \\ &\quad MainCharacters \rightarrow mainCharacters(\\ &\quad \quad MainCharacter^+), \\ &\quad MainCharacter \rightarrow mainCharacter(\varnothing), \\ &\quad \varnothing \rightarrow \theta(\epsilon)\} \end{aligned} $
--	--

Figure 4.4: XML document and a possible schema definition

<pre> { "title": "A Midsummer Night's Dream", "author": { "firstName": "William", "lastName": "Shakespeare" }, "authored": "1590–1596", "type": ["play", "comedy"], "mainCharacters": ["Duke of Athens", "Theseus", " Hippolyta"] } </pre>	$ \begin{aligned} N &= \{Resource, Title, Author, FName, \\ &\quad LName, Authored, Types, Type, \\ &\quad MainCharacters, MainCharacter, \\ &\quad \varnothing, \epsilon\} \\ R &= \{Resource\} \\ T_2 &= \{\#obj, title, author, firstName, \\ &\quad lastName, authored, type, \\ &\quad mainCharacters, \#arr, \theta\} \\ P_2 &= \{Resource \rightarrow \#obj(Title, Author, \\ &\quad Authored, Types, MainCharacters), \\ &\quad Title \rightarrow title(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Author \rightarrow author(FName, LName), \\ &\quad FName \rightarrow firstName(\varnothing), \\ &\quad LName \rightarrow lastName(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Authored \rightarrow authored(\varnothing), \\ &\quad Types \rightarrow type(Type^+), \\ &\quad Type \rightarrow \theta(\epsilon), \\ &\quad MainCharacters \rightarrow mainCharacters(\\ &\quad \quad MainCharacter^+), \\ &\quad MainCharacter \rightarrow \theta(\varnothing), \\ &\quad \varnothing \rightarrow \theta(\epsilon)\} \end{aligned} $
--	---

Figure 4.5: JSON document and a possible schema definition

The figures 4.4 and 4.5 present semantically equivalent grammars adapted for

the generation of XML and JSON based document trees. Whereas the terminals and production rules in figure 4.4 respects the distinction between elements and attributes in XML documents, figure 4.5 shows the adaption of the grammar to support objects and arrays as used within JSON. With respect to an implementation of the grammars in an integration system, such equivalent grammars could inherit the non-terminal and root symbols from an abstract super-implementation of the grammar and implement terminals and production rules in specific and derived grammars—assuming an object-oriented implementation.

4.4.2 Model integration

Metamodel integration encapsulates aspects of technical heterogeneity by interrelating external schema languages to their generic representation in terms of the integration model. In addition, for the generation of integrated views on heterogeneous semi-structured data, information on the semantic correlations between elements of relevant schemata are necessary. This dependency is indicated by the relation between schemata on the model-layer $M1$ in the four layer modeling architecture in figure 4.2.

Traditional approaches to data integration are based on the definition or creation of global views, which are determined according to the results from the requirements analysis of the application domain. A characteristic of the research data landscape of the arts and humanities consists in the diversity of collections, academic perspectives and research questions, which result in numerous, possibly conflicting information needs. In consequence, the definition of global views, which satisfy the requirements of completeness, correctness, minimality and understandability (BATINI ET AL. 1986, 337) on a holistic level is prevented. The central idea for integration in this thesis builds on the assumption that the applicability of schemata for the creation of integrative views depends on the information need associated with a particular integrative use-case.

Adopting the theoretical perspective of LENZERINI (2002, 234) accordingly, a data integration task provides a use-case oriented perspective on the selection of source and target schemata:

Definition 4.5 *A data integration task is a triple $\langle S_s, s_t, M \rangle$ with:*

- a set of source schemata S_s ,
- a target schema s_t and
- the set of mappings $M = \{m_{s_s \rightsquigarrow s_t} \mid s_s \in S_s\}$.

With respect to use-cases such as data consolidation or migration, data integration tasks are initiated by identifying the set of relevant source schemata, i.e. the schemata that are used by any of the data sources, which should be integrated. Based on the information needs and the availability of mappings, an appropriate target schema is determined. Mappings between a particular source and target schema contain the information required to transform a semi-structured document specified in terms of the source schema into the equivalent representation that conforms to the constraints of the target schema. As such, mappings are often considered as a set of correspondences between the semantically associated elements of the source and target schema (see e.g. [LESER & NAUMANN 2007](#), 125-126; [RAHM 2011](#), 4)—containing the rules necessary for data transformation and hence data integration. With respect to the field of schema matching, the interpretation of a mapping is plausible as a typical result of respective algorithms consists in the pairwise identification of elements, which indicate some similarity in terms of characteristics such as element labels or structural constraints ([RAHM 2011](#), 4; [SHVAIKO & EUZENAT 2005](#), 154).

[SHVAIKO & EUZENAT \(2013, 159\)](#) introduce the concept of correspondences as $\langle id, e_1, e_2, r \rangle$, which is compatibly extended by [GIUNCHIGLIA ET AL. \(2009\)](#) to $\langle id, e_1, e_2, n, r \rangle$, where:

- i is the identifier of the correspondence,
- e_1 refers to an element in the source schema,
- e_2 constitutes the correlated element in the target schema,
- n provides a confidence value for the correspondence to be true and
- r describes the relation between the elements e_1 and e_2 such as equivalence ($=$), more general (\sqsupseteq) or more specific (\sqsubseteq).

Despite the applicability of value correspondences for the description of the results of schema matching algorithms, there exists a semantic gap between value correspondences and semantically associated concept. Although correspondences provide information possibly sufficient to assist domain experts in identifying

and describing semantically correlated elements, the granularity level of value correspondences is not sufficient for data transformation. As a consequence, the notion of a concept mapping is introduced to describe semantic correlations:

Definition 4.6 *An concept mapping $cm = \langle E_{S_S}, E_{S_T}, f \rangle$ specifies a semantic correlation between a set of source elements E_{S_S} and corresponding target elements E_{S_T} , where*

- $E_{S_S} = \{e_{S_S,i} \dots e_{S_S,j}\} \mid e_{S_S} \in (N_{S_S} \cup L_{S_S})$
- $E_{S_T} = \{e_{S_T,k} \dots e_{S_T,l}\} \mid e_{S_T} \in (N_{S_T} \cup L_{S_T})$
- $f: E_{S_S} \rightarrow E_{S_T}$

Figure 4.6 shows three examples that indicate the relation between value correspondences and concept mappings and thereby illustrate the missing semantic in possibly automatically identified value correspondences. Java-oriented examples of data conversion functions are presented in listing 4.4:

- (a) The concept of a title in the source schema (*Title*) is represented by language-dependent title elements in the target schema (*Title_de*, *Title_en*). Despite the corresponding values, the value of the *Lang* attribute is required as conditional input for the specification of the function in the concept mapping.
- (b) *Type* is specified as a sub-element of *Person* in the target schema, whereas this conceptual detail is dependent on the structure in the source schema. The concept mapping thus aggregates structural information along with the input values of *ForeName* and *SurName* to compose the value of *Person* in the target schema.
- (c) Multiple nonterminal symbols or labels exist in the source schema, which are aggregated under on *Identifier* element in the target. A possible conversion rule could be based on a filter to use only one source identifier or—as exemplified in listing 4.4—combines values in terms of an array, leading to multiple *Identifier* elements in the target.

Element mappings describe of the aggregation and interpretation of value correspondences with the purpose of correlating heterogeneous representations of the same concept. In consequence, a schema mapping is composed of a set of concept mappings:

Definition 4.7 *A schema mapping $M_{S_S \rightsquigarrow S_T}$ is a set of mapping functions $m_1 \dots m_n$*

```
/**
 * Example (a)
 */
Element convertTitle(Element inLang, Element inTitle) {
    if (inLang.value.equals("de") || inLang.value.startsWith("de_")) {
        Element outTitleDe = new Element("Title_de");
        outTitleDe.value = inTitle.value;
        return outTitleDe;
    } else if (inLang.value.equals("en") || inLang.value.startsWith("en_")) {
        Element outTitleEn = new Element("Title_en");
        outTitleEn.value = inTitle.value;
        return outTitleEn;
    }
}

/**
 * Example (b)
 */
Element convertPerson(Element inCreator, Element inSurName, Element
    inForeName) {
    Element outPersonType = new Element("Type2");
    if (inCreator != null) {
        outPersonType.value = "creator";
    } else {
        outPersonType.value = "other";
    }
    Element outPerson = new Element("Person");
    outPerson.value = inSurName.value + ", " + inForeName.value;
    outPerson.subElements.add(outPersonType);
    return outPerson;
}

/**
 * Example (c)
 */
ElementArray convertIdentifiers(Element identifier1, Element identifier2) {
    ElementArray outIdentifierArr = new ElementArray("Identifier");
    if (inIdentifier1 != null) {
        Element outIdentifier = new Element();
        outIdentifier.value = inIdentifier1.value;
        outIdentifierArr.elements.add(outIdentifier);
    }
    if (inIdentifier2 != null) {
        Element outIdentifier = new Element();
        outIdentifier.value = inIdentifier2.value;
        outIdentifierArr.elements.add(outIdentifier);
    }
    return outIdentifierArr;
}
```

Listing 4.4: Java-oriented transformation functions for the concept mappings in figure 4.6

Figure 4.6: Exemplary concept mappings derived from value correspondences

defined over two structures S_S and S_T . For a particular pair of S_S and S_T only one schema mapping may exist.

Mappings form the result of the *design phase* of data integration and provide the information required of the *execution phase*. Metamodel matching describes the process of identifying semantic correlations between metamodels and can be executed manually by domain experts, supported by matching algorithms that require manual validation and correction and fully automatic.

4.5 Derivation strategy

The theoretical perspective introduced in the previous sections allows the format-independent representation of schemata in terms of a generic schema language. Two primary mechanisms for an enrichment of the schema semantics—in compari-

son to their external specifications—have been suggested:

- *Grammatical refinement* involves the modification of the sets of non-terminal and terminal symbols and related production rules to restrict the structure of expected data according to the implementations in digital collections.
- *Semantic enrichment* constitutes the possibility to assign labels to non-terminal symbols, which facilitates the explication of rules for data cleansing and processing and thus allows the generation of enriched content—while preserving original data as received from distributed sources.

With respect to the applications and use-cases of data integration in the context of the arts and humanities presented in the sections 3.3 and 3.4 respectively, a particular focus on vertical integration scenarios and hence use-cases with a limited set of relevant collections is noticeable:

- Both enrichment concepts are oriented towards the explication of knowledge about schemata in their specific interpretation in digital collections. This allows enriched semantics to be available for data integration, but also results in the definition of similar, but formally unrelated versions of a schema (such as DC in various specific usages).
- Mappings are created for one particular and possibly customized source and target schema, which is intended to result in a reduction of information loss when transforming data. However, the downside of this approach consists in the absence of mappings interrelating schemata for broader unifying views.

Considering an example, in which a number n of digital collections provide data in terms of simple DC. Based on the assumption that experts with a knowledge about each of the individual collections created and adapted a generic representation of a schema in order to increase structural and semantic information about data as provided by the sources, potentially n unrelated versions of DC are described in the information model and no unifying view could be generated—even though all collections use the same XML schema. To resolve this problem from a theoretical perspective, capabilities for the modularization and customization of schemata are introduced by the concept of derived schemata:

Definition 4.8 *A derived schema S' is a schema with a extended signature $S' = \langle N, T, R, L, F, P, S^* \rangle$, where S^* is a finite, nonempty set of super-schemata. S' is*

called a *derived schema* or *sub-schema* of S^* .

With the exception of the addition of S^* , the signature of a derived schema remains unchanged in order to leave previously stated explanations on schemata and mappings intact. However, this signature should be interpreted as a *black-box* view on a schema and—beside the designation of S' as derivation of the set of super-schemata S^* —definitions of preexisting components are conceptually modified. As such the sets of N , T and L of a derived schema share the common characteristic to be composed from the super-schemata, complemented by additional symbols and labels N^+ , T^+ and L^+ and reduced by explicit exclusions to the sets of inherited symbols and labels N^- , T^- and L^- :

Definition 4.9 *The set of non-terminal symbols N of a derived schema is composed of the non-terminal symbols of the super-schemata and additional non-terminal symbols N^+ . Any non-terminal symbol of a super-schema can be added to the set N^- , thereby excluding it from the available N of S' :*

$$\bigcup N := \{n \mid n \in N^+ \vee ((\exists k \in S^* : n \in N_k) \wedge n \notin N^-)\}$$

Definition 4.10 *The terminal symbols T of a derived schema include the terminal symbols of the super-schemata and additional terminal symbols T^+ . Any terminal symbol of a super-schema added to T^- is excluded from T of S' :*

$$\bigcup T := \{t \mid t \in T^+ \vee ((\exists k \in S^* : t \in T_k) \wedge t \notin T^-)\}$$

Definition 4.11 *The set of labels L defined for a derived schema is composed of the labels of the super-schemata S^* and additional labels L^+ . Any label of a super-schema added to L^- is excluded from L of S' :*

$$\bigcup L := \{l \mid l \in L^+ \vee ((\exists k \in S^* : l \in L_k) \wedge l \notin L^-)\}$$

As the definitions of the production rules ($n \rightarrow te_c$ with $n \in N$ and $t \in T$, see section 4.3) and labeling functions ($x \rightarrow le_l$ with $x \in (N \cup L)$ and $l \in L$, see section 4.3) remain formally unmodified, they reference N , T and L of the derived schema and are additionally extended and restricted by the according sets of P^+ , F^+ , P^- and L^- :

Definition 4.12 *The set of production rules P of S' is composed of all production rules of the super-schemata S^* that are valid against the composed sets of N and T of the derived schema S' . Additional production rules defined in the set P^+ are included in P , any production rule of a super-schema can be marked as excluded by adding it to P^-*

Definition 4.13 *The set of labeling functions F of a derived schema S' is composed of the labeling functions of all designated super-schemata S^* , for which both the associated non-terminal symbol and label are contained in N and L respectively. Any particular labeling function of a super-schema can be excluded from F by its addition to F^- , additional functions can be registered by their addition to F^+*

In the remainder of this section, the derivation concept is exemplified according to two scenarios, which are considered to be the main use-cases for derivation: the composition of schemata to facilitate modularization and the customization of generic schemata to their specific usage in digital collections.

4.5.1 Composite schemata

One particular use-case for schema derivation can be inferred from the capabilities of the W3C XML schema language, which allows the specification of composite XML schemata (THOMPSON ET AL. 2012, Sect. 4.2). As a consequence, the constraints of XML schemata can be assembled and reused in composite schemata—facilitating the reduction of redundancy.

```
<xs:schema targetNamespace="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/xMetaDiss/"
  xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
  xmlns:ddb="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/ddb/"
  xmlns:pc="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/pc/"
  xmlns="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/xMetaDiss/"
  ...
  <xs:import namespace="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
    schemaLocation="http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2006/01/06/dc.
      xsd"/>
  <xs:import namespace="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/ddb/"
    schemaLocation="ddb.xsd"/>
  <xs:import namespace="http://www.d-nb.de/standards/pc/"
    schemaLocation="pc.xsd"/>
  ...
```

```
<xs:element name="xMetaDiss">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element ref="dc:title" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
      <xs:element ref="dc:creator" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
      <xs:element ref="dc:subject" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
      ...
      <xs:element ref="dc:identifier"/>
      ...
      <xs:element ref="ddb:contact"/>
      ...
      <xs:element ref="ddb:identifier" minOccurs="0"
        maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
      ...
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:schema>
```

Listing 4.5: Excerpt of the schema for XMetaDiss¹⁹

In comparison to the mechanisms in the W3C XML schema language, the extended definition of schemata allows the specification of a derived schema from a set of super-schemata with comparable grammatical results. Despite the initial similarity of 'schema composition' and 'schema derivation', the terminological difference is intentional and relates to the role of the imported/parent schemata: Revisiting the example presented in section 4.3 please notice that the XML schema for the XMetaDissPlus specification forms a composite schema in terms of W3C XML schema. Figure 4.5 shows the parts of the XMetaDissPlus XML schema that is relevant for the example.

Based on the extended schema definition, the grammar of XMetaDissPlus can be summarized as in table 4.3. Figure 4.7 shows the interpretation of the XML document that has been introduced in listing 4.1 indicating the definition areas of the super-schemata of which the presented excerpt is based.

4.5.2 Collection-specific customization

Aside from the representation of composite schemata, the adaption to the specific usage in particular communities or individual collections forms another important use-case for schema derivation: As previously stated, research objects and

¹⁹ <http://files.dnb.de/standards/xmetadiss/xmetadiss.xsd>

$N^+ = \{XMetaDiss\}$
$N^- = \emptyset$
$T^+ = \{xmd : xMetaDiss\}$
$T^- = \emptyset$
$R = \{XMetaDiss\}$
$P^+ = \{XMetaDiss \rightarrow xmd : xMetaDiss($ $DC.Title^+, DC.Creator^+, DC.Subject^+,$ $DC.Identifier, DDB.Contact,$ $DDB.Identifier^*)\}$
$P^- = \emptyset$
$L^+ = \emptyset$
$L^- = \emptyset$
$F^+ = \emptyset$
$F^- = \emptyset$

Table 4.3: Derived grammar based on the exemplary XMetaDiss schema

their descriptions are assembled within the specific environment of disciplines, research projects and the containing collections, which leads to a context-specific interpretation or adaption of specified schemata.

Aside from the XML document in section 4.3.2, an example for an adaption of a particularly generic schema has been presented in the exemplary XML document obtained from Pangaea (see listing 3.1). Within the document, elements including dc:coverage and dc:creator can be decomposed into atomic values, which can formally be described based on the semantic extension of schemata by labels L and labeling functions F as indicated in section 4.3. With the help of the schema derivation concept, such use-cases for the customization of schemata according to concrete usage scenarios can be explicated, while ensuring the interoperability benefits are conserved.

Schema customization is not limited to the concepts of labels, but can also be performed on the grammatical components of the schema definition. Assuming that a collection provides documents that are specified according a custom extension of the XMetaDissPlus XML schema. Within this particular schema, the dc:creator element is not filled according to the original schema, but reverts to a simple XML type. Within the dc:creator field, instances of the custom schema reference entries

Figure 4.7: Interpretation of the example in 4.1 with as composite tree

in a person reference database by an id. With the help of schema derivation, the XMetaDissPlus specification can be derived to respect this modification, while leaving other fields as well as the validity of the mappings intact.

4.5.3 Mapping inheritance

In order to prepare the re-usability and customization of mappings, the concept of a derived schema mapping is finally introduced as:

Definition 4.14 A derived schema mapping M' is a schema mapping with an extended signature $M_{S_S \rightsquigarrow S_T} = \langle S_S, S_T, M^* \rangle$, where

- S_S constitutes the source schema,
- S_T is the target schema and
- M^* is a set of super-mappings.

Comparable with schemata, a derived mappings reuses concept mappings from the set of super-schemata. Based on additionally defined mappings $m_1^+ \dots m_n^+$, the sets of available concept mappings is extended—invalidated mappings are defined in $m_1^- \dots m_n^-$.

A simplification for implementations of the generic model could consist in the creation of a derived mapping for each of the mappings associated with a schema, as soon as this particular schema is derived.

5

Chapter Summary

After the introduction in chapter 1, abstract characteristics of semi-structured data as well as specific formats, i.e. [XML](#), [JSON](#) and [YAML](#) have been introduced in chapter 2—along with a classification and introduction of the problem areas of data integration that result from heterogeneity on various levels.

Central aspects of the context of the arts and humanities have been presented in chapter 3: The application domain is primarily characterized by a large set of digital collections and numerous schemata, to which their contained data conforms. This heterogeneity, along with the diversity of disciplines and research questions prevents the selection or creation of a particular integrative schema. Instead, the abstract use-cases have been used to derive the central assumption of this thesis, that a generic integration model in the sense of a framework for the continuous explication of knowledge provides a more suitable response to the specific context of the arts and humanities.

For this reason, chapter 4 presented a conceptual architecture based on so called semantic clusters that provide discipline- or use-case-specific views and whose interconnection leads to the continuous evolution of global, unifying perspectives over the research data landscape. After a definition of the formal terminology, the concept has been developed on the basis of a formal schema definition. Based on conceptual mappings that are aggregated in terms of schema mappings, semantic correlations can be specified. The proposal of a derivation strategy extends the integration model with particular respect to scalability and concludes the concept

of the thesis.

In summary, this thesis provides a theoretical approach to represent enriched versions of heterogeneous schemata for semi-structured data. Based on regular tree grammars, the presented model constitutes a format- and technology-independent concept for the integration of research data in the context of the arts and humanities. As a result of the abstraction from technological problems, fundamental semantic aspects have been highlighted, whose resolution depends on the explication of the background knowledge of domain experts. An integrative system based on the presented model is enabled to classify issues of data integration into technological and context-dependent components—allowing the differentiated realization of the data integration concept in terms of (1) adaptations to identifiable access protocols and schema languages—implementable mainly by software engineers and (2) models of schemata and mappings, which are continuously described and refined by scholars and research projects.

The model presents various extension points, among which the association of labels to entries in controlled vocabularies or ontologies seems intuitive in order to further enhance the semantic richness of represented schemata and provide unifying views based on ontological relations.

Bibliography

- Abiteboul, S (2009):** *Semi-Structured Data*. In: Liu, L; Özsu, MT (Eds.): Encyclopedia of Database Systems, pp.2599–2601. Springer US, Boston and MA, 2009. ISBN:0387399402.
- Atkinson, C; Kühne, T (2003):** *Model-driven development*. In: IEEE Software, 20(5): 36–41.
- Batini, C; Lenzerini, M; Navathe, SB (1986):** *A comparative analysis of methodologies for database schema integration*. In: ACM Computing Surveys, 18(4):323–364.
- Ben-Kiki, O; Evans, C; döt Net, I (2009):** *YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML™): Version 1.2*, 2009. <http://www.yaml.org/spec/1.2/spec.html>, (Last checked: 2014-01-20).
- Bézivin, J (2005):** *On the unification power of models*. In: Software & Systems Modeling, 4 (2):171–188.
- Bray, T; Paoli, J; Sperberg-McQueen, CM; Maler, E; Yergeau, F; Cowan, J (2006):** *Extensible Markup Language (XML) 1.1 (Second Edition): W3C Recommendation*, 2006. <http://www.w3.org/TR/2006/REC-xml11-20060816/>, (Last checked: 2014-01-12).
- Buneman, P (1997):** *Semistructured data*. In: Mendelzon, A; Özsoyoglu, ZM (Eds.): Proceedings of the sixteenth ACM SIGACT-SIGMOD-SIGART symposium on Principles of database systems, pp.117–121. ACM, 1997.
- Clark, T; Sammut, P; Willans, J (2008):** *Applied metamodelling: A foundation for language driven development*, 2008. <https://eprints.mdx.ac.uk/6060/>, (Last checked: 2013-12-02).
- DASISH (2013):** *Data Service Infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2013. http://dasish.eu/publications/projectreports/D2.1_-_State_of_the_Architectures_Report.pdf, (Last checked: 2013-10-12).
- DCMI (2012):** *Dublin Core Metadata Element Set, Version 1.1*, 2012. <http://dublincore.org/documents/dces/>, (Last checked: 2013-10-10).

- Falconer, SM; Noy, NF (2011):** *Interactive Techniques to Support Ontology Matching*. In: Bellahsene, Z; Bonifati, A; Rahm, E (Eds.): *Schema Matching and Mapping*, pp.29–51. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2011. ISBN:978-3-642-16517-7.
- Galiegue, F; Zyp, K; Court, G (2013):** *JSON Schema: core definitions and terminology: IETF Internet-Draft*, 2013. <http://json-schema.org/latest/json-schema-core.html>, (Last checked: 2014-01-20).
- Gill, T (2008):** *Metadata and the Web*. In: Baca, M (Ed.): *Introduction to metadata*, pp.20–37. Getty Research Institute, Los Angeles and CA, 2008. ISBN:0892368969.
- Giunchiglia, F; Yatskevich, M; Avesani, P; Shivaiko, P (2009):** *A large dataset for the evaluation of ontology matching*. In: *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, 24(2): 137–157.
- Hagedorn, K (2003):** *OAlster: a "no dead ends" OAI service provider*. In: *Library Hi Tech*, 21(2):170–181.
- Hockey, S (2004):** *The History of Humanities Computing*. In: Schreibman, S; Siemens, RG; Unsworth, J (Eds.): *A companion to digital humanities (Blackwell companions to literature and culture, 26)*. Blackwell Pub., Malden and Mass, 2004. ISBN:1405168064. http://nora.lis.uiuc.edu:3030/companion/view?docId=blackwell/9781405103213/9781405103213.xml&doc.view=content&chunk.id=ss1-2-1&toc.depth=1&brand=9781405103213_brand&anchor.id=0.
- Kett, J (2005):** *MABxml-1: Ein XML-Schema für das MAB2-Format: Dokumentation. Version 1.2*, 2005. <http://www.dnb.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/DNB/standardisierung/kettMabXml1Version1.2Dokumentation2005.pdf>, (Last checked: 2014-01-02).
- Lagoze, C; Van de Sompel, Herbert; Nelson, M; Warner, S (2002):** *The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting*, 2002. <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>, (Last checked: 2014-01-13).
- Lenzerini, M (2002):** *Data Integration: A Theoretical Perspective*. In: Abiteboul, S (Ed.): *Proceedings of the twenty-first ACM SIGMOD-SIGACT-SIGART symposium on Principles of database systems*, p. 233. ACM, 2002. ISBN:9781581135077.
- Leser, U; Naumann, F (2007):** *Informationsintegration: Architekturen und Methoden zur Integration verteilter und heterogener Datenquellen*. 1st edn, Dpunkt-Verl., Heidelberg. ISBN:9783898644006.
- Mani, M; Lee, D; Muntz, RR (2001):** *Semantic Data Modeling Using XML Schemas*. In:

S.Kunii, H; Jajodia, S; Sølvsberg, A (Eds.): *Conceptual Modeling — ER 2001* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 2224), pp.149–163. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2001. ISBN:978-3-540-42866-4.

Murata, M; Lee, D; Mani, M; Kawaguchi, K (2005): *Taxonomy of XML schema languages using formal language theory*. In: *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology*, 5(4):660–704.

Nečaský, M; Mlýnková, I (2010): *When Conceptual Model Meets Grammar: A Formal Approach to Semi-structured Data Modeling*. In: Hutchison, D; Kanade, T; Kittler, J; Kleinberg, JM; Mattern, F; Mitchell, JC; Naor, M; Nierstrasz, O; Pandu Rangan, C; Steffen, B; Sudan, M; Terzopoulos, D; Tygar, D; Vardi, MY; Weikum, G; Chen, L; Triantafillou, P; Suel, T (Eds.): *Web Information Systems Engineering – WISE 2010* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 6488), pp.279–293. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2010. ISBN:978-3-642-17615-9.

Peroni, S; Tomasi, F; Vitali, F (2013): *Reflecting on the Europeana Data Model*. In: Agosti, M; Esposito, F; Ferilli, S; Ferro, N (Eds.): *Digital Libraries and Archives* (Communications in Computer and Information Science, 354), pp.228–240. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2013. ISBN:978-3-642-35833-3.

Polfreman, M (2005): *Commonly-used metadata formats in the Arts and Humanities*, 2005. <http://www.ahds.ac.uk/metadata/arts-humanities-metadata-formats.htm>, (Last checked: 2013-11-04).

Rahm, E (2011): *Towards Large-Scale Schema and Ontology Matching*. In: Bellahsene, Z; Bonifati, A; Rahm, E (Eds.): *Schema Matching and Mapping*, pp.3–27. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2011. ISBN:978-3-642-16517-7.

Shvaiko, P; Euzenat, J (2005): *A Survey of Schema-Based Matching Approaches*. In: Hutchison, D; Kanade, T; Kittler, J; Kleinberg, JM; Mattern, F; Mitchell, JC; Naor, M; Nierstrasz, O; Pandu Rangan, C; Steffen, B; Sudan, M; Terzopoulos, D; Tygar, D; Vardi, MY; Weikum, G; Spaccapietra, S (Eds.): *Journal on Data Semantics IV* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 3730), pp.146–171. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin and Heidelberg, 2005. ISBN:978-3-540-31001-3.

Shvaiko, P; Euzenat, J (2013): *Ontology Matching: State of the Art and Future Challenges*. In: *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, 25(1):158–176.

Suciu, D (2009): *Semi-Structured Data Model*. In: Liu, L; Özsu, MT (Eds.): *Encyclopedia of Database Systems*, pp.2601–2605. Springer US, Boston and MA, 2009. ISBN:0387399402.

Thompson, HS; Mendelsohn, N; Beech, D; Maloney, M (2012): *W3C XML Schema Definition Language (XSD) 1.1: Part 1: Structures*, 2012.

<http://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-xmlschema11-1-20120405/>, (Last checked: 2013-11-11).

University of Michigan (2011): *OAster Statistics*, 2011.

<http://www.lib.umich.edu/digital-library-production-service-dlps/oaister-statistics>, (Last checked: 2013-01-04).

Vierkant, P (2013): *Leuchttürme der deutschen Repositorienlandschaft*, 2013. <http://de.slideshare.net/paulvierkant/leuchttirme-der-deutschen-repositorienlandschaft>,

(Last checked: 2013-11-04).

Zhang, Z; Che, H; Shi, P; Sun, Y; Gu, J (2005): *An Algebraic Framework for Schema Matching*. In: Fan, W; Wu Zhaohui; Yang, J (Eds.): *Advances in Web-Age Information Management (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 3739)*, pp.694–699. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2005. ISBN:978-3-540-29227-2.

Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Ich erkläre hiermit gemäß §16 der Prüfungsordnung für den Masterstudiengang VAWi, dass ich die vorliegende Projektarbeit mit dem Titel „Towards the federation of digital collections within the arts and humanities - concept of a generic integration model for semi-structured research data“ selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Hilfsmittel und Quellen benutzt, Zitate kenntlich gemacht und die Arbeit noch keiner anderen Stelle zu Prüfungszwecken vorgelegt habe.

Ort, Datum

Tobias Gradl